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Second dissemination event

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Introduction

The present deliverable is meant to report about the second of the two major dissemination events organised by the consortium to present the project and demo its prototype system to general public and peers in the research, clinical and industry sectors. Besides the EU Digital Assembly (Sofia, 25-26 June 2018), reported in *D10.3 - First dissemination event* as 'first dissemination event' for being the first public demo of the MHMD system, another major opportunity for project dissemination was offered by ICT 2018 (Vienna, 4-6 December 2018), the research and innovation participatory event organised by the European Commission and the Austrian Presidency of the Council of the European Union, which attracted about 4,800 visitors among science community members, policymakers and citizens. The report will thus detail the event and Consortium participation, including a *project booth* – including posters, brochures and a live system demo - and the three *networking sessions* organised within the event, along with other dissemination and outreach activities.

Along with that, the report will also give an account of the other minor dissemination events organised/attended by the whole consortium or its partners (individually) in the second reporting period (M19-M36), as well as planned for the next months until the end of the project. These include research conferences and public networking events in the field of health IT, personal data, AI, blockchain and ICT for health, organised at institutional or industry level. There, Project Coordinator and other Consortium partners have presented the project or its emerging innovations (e.g., synthetic data, homomorphic encryption, etc.) with relevant academic communities, industry stakeholders, policy makers and mass media representatives, chaired and animated sessions on relevant themes (e.g., personal data, health data, blockchain in health, ICT for health), and posed the base for further cross-fertilisation, feedback gathering from peers in the clinical and IT community and possible exploitation routes for the future project sustainability.

1 ICT 2018: Imagine Digital - Connect Europe

VIENNA
4-6 DECEMBER

When	4-6 December 2018	Where	Vienna, Austria	Venue	Austria Center
Theme	<i>Imagine digital – connect Europe</i>				
Details	This research and innovation event focused on the European Union's priorities in the digital transformation of society and industry, as an opportunity for the people involved in this transformation to share their experience and vision of Europe in the digital age				
Organisers	European Commission and the Austrian Presidency of the Council of the European Union				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Davide Zaccagnini, Mirko De Maldè, Anna Rizzo, Lynkeus Lucian Itu, Cosmin Nita, Anamaria Vizitiu, UTBV Yannis Ioannidis, Minos Garofalakis, Athena RC Rudolf Mayer, SBA				
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exhibition booth: MyHealthMyData (MHMD) • Networking sessions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Blockchain applications in healthcare data management and exchange 2. Realizing the promise of in-silico medicine: challenges and opportunities in clinical implementation 3. Secure genomic data sharing with encryption-based privacy preserving tools 				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn	Public	Science community members, policymakers, fellow ICT-enthusiasts, citizens		
Event material	Website				

1.1 The event

ICT 2018 is the European Commission's flagship event on research, innovation and digitalisation. It focuses on the European Union's strategy and programmes regarding the digital transformation of society, economy and industry, and represents an opportunity for people involved in Europe's digital transformation to share their experience and vision. This year, the event was articulated through four main components: (1) conferences, (2) exhibitions, (3) networking opportunities and an (4) innovation and start-ups forum.

1. The **conference** programme featured debates around the EU's digital policy with 6 plenary sessions on topics such as Artificial Intelligence, Next Generation Internet, Digital Skills and High-Performance Computing. Influential speakers from policy circles and public bodies, academia, industry, civil society and industry highlighted their perspectives and priorities, and discussed how each can contribute to the successful

digital transformation of Europe. The event also hosted IMAGINE18, the annual conference of the Austrian ICT community, which revolved around the theme "Technologies bridging Generations" with digital experts, policy makers and researchers, together with young students, reflecting on future scenarios and developments in the field of ICT and its effects on daily life.

2. The event included a 5.000 m² **exhibition area** showcasing the best accomplishments and pioneering results, innovative products and services emerging from EU-funded research and innovation actions, international cooperation and Austrian initiatives, to connect today's research and innovation with visions for the future. The whole spectrum of digital and ICT topics was covered, with more than 100 exhibits ranging from digital society to transforming industry and economy, and the most recent technological advancements, giving them the opportunity to find investors, buyers or business partners to make their results market-ready. The ICT 2018 exhibition included, among others, the following main areas:

The whole spectrum of digital and ICT topics was covered, with more than 100 exhibits ranging from digital society to transforming industry and economy, and the most recent technological advancements, giving them the opportunity to find investors, buyers or business partners to make their results market-ready. The ICT 2018 exhibition included, among others, the following main areas:

- 1) **General Exhibition**, a major exhibition of EU-funded research and innovation projects from current and previous framework programmes around three themes: Inspiring a digital society; Creating networks and technology; and Transforming industry and economy.
- 2) **International Cooperation (INCO) Village**, displaying successful international collaborations with the EU's key partners from around the world (South Korea, Japan, Brazil, South Africa and other international partners);

- 3) **Innovation and Start-ups Village**, promoting EU-funded start-ups and displaying innovative services or products that were looking for opportunities to enter the market;
- 4) **European Commission (EC) Village**, providing thorough information about EU flagship initiatives on telecom, research and innovation, open science and more;
- 5) **The Austrian Village**, hosting an exhibition with highlights from the Austrian research community, covering a broad range of ICT applications in economy and society.

3. A number of offline and online **networking opportunities** were offered for participants to meet and engage with the academic and research community, decision-makers, as well as business representatives. Among them, thematic networking sessions were organised by stakeholders attending to boost exchanges between participants, in the form of informal group discussions that seek brainstorming and active interactions, in view of developing new

partnerships for research and innovation. Also, a Face2Face brokerage event composed of short, prearranged meetings, provided an additional way of networking and possibly meeting potential cooperation partners at the event.

4. The **Innovation and Startups forum** has been a dedicated conference with workshops, innovation exhibits and marketplace, to explore and debate the development and use of disruptive technologies for economic growth, human development and addressing societal challenges. The forum showcased cutting-edge innovations from across Europe and brought together start-ups, innovators, policy makers, governments and investors for policy dialogues, workshops and collaboration.

1.2 MHMD at ICT2018

The MHMD consortium took part in ICT2018 with various initiatives, including an exhibition booth and two networking sessions, along with the participation of its members to several other conference meetings, networking and outreach activities. The participation of MHMD to the overall event as well as its specific initiatives were widely showcased through the project website and social media accounts, before as well as with live feeds during the three days of the event and echoed by relevant channels.

1.2.1 The exhibition booth

The MHMD exhibition booth was held within the *Inspiring a Digital Society* exhibition area (Hall X3, stand i10), based on the indicated keywords *eHealth, AI, big data, blockchain*. The exhibition focus topic, as indicated in the application and exhibition catalogue, was described as follows.

Taking back control of your health data

Medical data is generally stored in separate locations and is not always easily accessible to patients and research institutions. It can be vulnerable to security breaches and identity theft and at the same time scientists do not always have access to data for biomedical research and for developing new treatments. My Health My Data (MHMD) aims to use blockchain technology to enable medical data to be stored and transmitted safely and effectively. MHMD project is centred on the connection between organisations and individuals. It encourages hospitals to start making anonymised data available for open research, while prompting citizens to become the ultimate owners and controllers of their health data.

The booth included several posters (standard 50x70 and roll-up banners) focusing on (1) general project overview, (2) legal aspects (i.e., novelties introduced by the GDPR and the MHMD compliance model), for GDPR, (3) MHMD stakeholders and the system data flow, (4) user interfaces for individuals' onboarding and consent management through the MHMD app. Also, the booth was provided with a video screen, which was used by the PC and his team execute the live demo of platform and, between demos, for a general video explaining MHMD main features and tools, displayed in a loop.

The live demo offered an end-to-end demonstration of the data workflow from the perspective of a hospital (with data registration and setting of access permissions) and a researcher (browsing the catalogue and requiring data), showcasing the data catalogue, the blockchain explorer, the web interfaces, and the mobile app. In this way, the Consortium had the chance to communicate the overall project objectives and intermediate results, as well as give a general view of its working system in front of a variety of stakeholders from industry, SMEs and academia, EC and mass media representatives.

Among other projects, MHMD was given a space by the EC press office, in the form of an interview and live demo of the system by the PC. Besides, another representative from the Project Coordinator's team was invited to a live radio webcasting hosted by the Digital Single Market Press Room, with the participation of MP Eva Kaili and the head of Unit of the Digital Innovation and Blockchain Peteris Zilgalvis.

1.2.2 Networking sessions

The PC and his team also organised two networking sessions, aimed at presenting MHMD-related innovation and boost the public debate on relevant themes such as healthcare blockchain, AI, and privacy preserving technologies, also in view of fostering potential collaboration for the establishment of research consortia or public-private partnerships.

1.2.2.1 Networking session “Blockchain applications in healthcare”

The networking session on blockchain application in healthcare was aimed at presenting the MHMD technological approach and establish potential collaborations with industry members and enforce connection with other relevant communities, through an open debate on standards and remaining challenges for the widespread adoption of blockchain solutions in the health domain. The session was promoted through social media and printed leaflets distributed before the event. As a result, the session was very well received, allowing to fill the room (+100 seats).

Networking session: Blockchain applications in healthcare data management and exchange

Room M1, 05/12/2018 (10:00-10:45)

The potential of the blockchain technology in the healthcare domain has been recognized by several stakeholders around the world, with applications spanning from health data exchange and identity management to drugs supply chain, from insurance to personalized medicine. The session is dedicated to discussing potential applications, various possible models and relevant technological implementations and challenges for making the best use of DLTs in the health domain.

In particular, the networking session will focus on:

- 1) new models of data mobilisation and relevant consent and permission management, looking into the experience of the EU-funded project *MyHealthMyData*;
- 2) innovative approaches for data self-sovereignty and patient-centric distributed data analytics, discussing the system implemented by the Swedish company *CareChain.io*;
- 3) the alternative DLTs approach presented by *Hedera Hashgraph* and its innovative consensus protocol, capable of performing up to 200.000 transactions per second without energy-hungry computational processes, and its potential impact on Medical IoT;
- 4) the innovative Natural Blockchain Language, implemented at the *Blockchain Knowledge Foundation*, which allows to “translate” the formal natural language of a given agreement into an error-free smart contract.

The session will be organised as follow:

- 10:00 – 10:25: quickfire presentations of the 4 panellists;
- 10:25 – 10:45: panel discussion with the involvement of the attendees

SPEAKERS

Mirko De Maldè, Lynkeus (Moderator)
 Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus, Coordinator of MyHealthMyData
 Johan Sellström, Co-founder at CareChain.io
 Peo Strömberg, Hedera Hashgraph Head of Strategic Partnership EMEA
 Arnoud W. Berghuis, Founder of the Blockchain Knowledge Foundation

1.2.2.2 Networking session “Secure genomic data sharing with encryption-based privacy preserving tools”

The session was organised taking inspiration from the European Union’s [Declaration on cross-border access to genomic databases](#), signed by 13 European countries for an enhanced sharing of genomic data to improve understanding and prevention of disease, development of personalised treatments – including targeted drugs – particularly for rare diseases, cancer and brain related diseases. The focus of the session, i.e., secure and privacy preserving genomic data sharing, allowed to pursue two objectives: on the one hand, to present the security and privacy-preserving tools developed within MHMD, i.e., the Secure Multi-Party Computation (Athena RC) and the Homomorphic Encryption (UTBV) protocols; on the other, to illustrate the potential of using synthetic data in genomics. Besides promoting the session via social media and a print-based leaflet, the session received increased visibility thanks to the [Innovation Radar Prize 2018](#), an EC initiative to identify high-potential innovations and innovators in EU-funded research and innovation projects. The Prize featured 5 categories, namely (1) Best Young SME, (2) Industrial & Enabling Tech, (3) Best early stage innovation, (4) Tech for Society and (5) Excellent Science 2018. Among others, Transylvania University of Brasov (UTBV) was selected among the Finalists of the [Industrial & Enabling Tech](#) category, for its [Deep Learning-based model for homomorphic encryption](#) developed within MHMD. Despite not being awarded the prize in favour of New Infrared Technologies (NIT), the Innovation Radar represented an important occasion to showcase project results and animate the session, thanks to the presence of Lucian Itu and his team (Cosmin Nita, Anamaria Vizitiu).

Secure genomic data sharing with encryption-based privacy preserving tools

Room 2.95, 06/12/2018 (11:30-12:15)

Making at least 1 Mii genomes accessible by 2022 is the target set by the EU in the [Declaration on cross-border access to genomic databases](#) (10 April 2018). To pinpoint disease genetic bases, large datasets have to be gathered through vast collaborative efforts. Meanwhile, genetic data represent very sensitive information carrying high risk of identification, needing special protection.

To this end, different types of *privacy-preserving* (PP) methods can be put in place to avoid disclosure, such as AI-based *homomorphic encryption* (HE) or *secure multi-party computation* (SMC), which allow distrustful parties to perform computation directly on encrypted data or in a distributed manner, while remaining oblivious to the input data and the intermediate results.

Another approach is based on generating *synthetic data*, artificial data generated by machine learning algorithms through recursive conditional parameter aggregation. While retaining significant information, these data do not belong *by definition* to any existing person, which puts them out of the scope of the GDPR and make them freely tradeable. Synthetic replicas of *gene expression*, *single nucleotide polymorphism*, *copy number variation* or *protein-protein/gene-gene interaction* data are possible ways for dealing with the genome-sharing challenge.

SPEAKERS

Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus
 Davide Zaccagnini, Lynkeus
 Lucian Itu, Transylvania University of Brasov
 Minos Garofalakis, Athena Research and Innovation Centre

Innovation Radar Finalists

Best early stage innovation	Bionicia Sygic Xlab Sintef
Industrial & Enabling Tech	Transilvania University of Brasov New Infrared Technologies GlassUp Orbe
Best Young SME	Spazio Dati Multiwave Technologies Energica Motor InoSens
Excellent Science	Fresnel Institute AvantiCell Science Technical University of Denmark University of Zagreb
Tech for Society	Friedrich-Schiller-University JENA Gr3n University of Iceland Ifinity

#InnovationRadar
 @ICTInnovEU
 bit.ly/InnoRadarEU

2 Other dissemination events (M19-M36)

2.1 Dissemination events in Y2 (M19-M24)

2.1.1 eHealth2018

When	8-9 May 2018	Where	Vienna, Austria	Venue	Schonbrunn Palace
Theme	12th Annual Conference on Health Informatics meets eHealth				
Details	The event provides a platform for researchers, practitioners, decision makers and vendors to discuss innovative health informatics and eHealth solutions so as to improve the quality and efficiency of health care.				
Organisers	Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT), the Austrian Working Group of Health Informatics and eHealth				
Who	Peter Kieseberg, SBA				
What	Presentation on the theme “Trusted data sharing enabled by blockchain technology”, with mention to MHMD				
Dissemination	-	Public	Academia, clinicians, decision makers		
Event material	Website				

MyHealthMyData at a glance

- Duration: November 2016 – October 2019
- 9 Research Partners
- 4 Clinical partners:
- 1 Legal consultancy:
- 1 Industry:

2.1.2 Big Data Value Meet-up Sofia

When	14-16 May 2018	Where	Sofia, Bulgaria	Venue	-
Topics	Digital health, ICT for health				
Details	The event has the twofold objective of strengthening collaborations among community members and increasing the visibility and awareness about the PPP in East Europe in general and Bulgaria in particular				
Organisers	Big Data Value Association				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Presentation of the progress status of MHMD, presentation and networking				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook	Public	Industry and SME, policy makers		
Event material	Website				

2.1.3 HIMSS Europe 18 and Health 2.0 Conference

When	27-29 May 2018	Where	Sitges, Spain	Venue	Melia Hotel
Topics	Digital health, ICT for health				
Details	The joint HIMSS Europe and Health 2.0 aims to gather digital health professionals from Europe and overseas to explore international innovations in consumer health, patient care, digital healthcare technologies, big data and analytics, AI and wearable tech, to initiate meaningful conversations and to create digital health marketplaces				
Organisers	HIMSS Europe				
Who	Mirko DE Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Speaker within two sessions: <i>Playing with blockchain</i> , giving an introduction to the blockchain technology through a puzzle game, and <i>Personal Health Record (PHR) initiative session "Empowering Patients and Citizens to Become CEOs of their Own Health"</i> , with presentation of MHMD, exploring the emerging landscape of personal health record initiatives, particularly what they promise and how are they delivering on those promises				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook	Public	Clinicians, industry and SME, policy makers, patients' associations		
Event material	Website				

2.1.4 eHealthWorld Monaco 2018

When	31 May – 1 June 2018	Where	Principality of Monaco	Venue	Melia Hotel
Topics	Digital health, ICT for health				
Details	eHM2018 was organised by healthcare professionals of all specialities with the objective of achieving constant progresses in the taking charge of patients, diagnostics, treatment and prevention with the support of emerging ICT applications. eHM2018 aimed to boost cooperation between clinicians and patients, MedTech and Drug Tech industry, payers and regulators.				
Organisers	Association e-HealthWorld Monaco				
Who	David Manset, gnùbila				
What	Speaker within the session “Edhec: enjoy business in eHealth”, in Salle Atelier (31 May, 14:15).				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook	Public	Clinicians, industry and SME, policy makers, patients’ associations		
Event material	Website				

2.1.5 Digital Assembly 2018

When	25-26 June 2018	Where	Sofia, Bulgaria	Venue	National Palace of Culture
Topics	Digital transformation in Europe				
Details	The event represents a forum for stakeholders to debate, take stock and look ahead at how Europe and its partners around the world are preparing for the main digital policy challenges ahead, and offers the opportunity for dialogue on their potential benefits for citizens and businesses				
Organisers	European Commission, Bulgarian Presidency of the Council of the European Union				
Who	All consortium				
What	MHMD booth and live demo				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook	Public	EU member state representatives and policy makers upon invitation		
Event material	Website				

2.1.6 Malta Blockchain Summit 2018

When	1-2 November 2018	Where	St. Julian's, Malta	Venue	InterContinental Arena
Topics	Blockchain applications in a variety of fields including Health, Entertainment, Government, Banking, Payments and Fintech				
Details	The Summit represented a melting pot for global influencers in technology, civil society, democracy promotion and innovation. It focused on world-changing potential applications of the Blockchain across multiple verticals, including, but not limited to, Health, Entertainment, Government, Banking, Payments and Fintech, and more. The summit reached 4000 delegates worldwide and featured a Hackathon and an ICO pitch, connecting investors with ICOs.				
Organisers	Maltese Government				
Who	Mirko de Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Speaker in a blockchain in healthcare-relevant sessions				
Dissemination	-	Public	Global influencers in technology, civil society, democracy promotion and innovation		
Event material	Website				

2.1.7 International Data Week 2018 (IDW 2018)

When	5-8 November 2018	Where	Gaborone, Botswana	Venue	Botswana Open Science and Open Data Forum
Topics	"The Digital Frontiers of Global Science"				
Details	<p>IDW 2018 brought together data scientists, researchers, industry leaders, entrepreneurs, policymakers and data stewards from all disciplines and geographies across the globe. Co-organized by the ISC World Data System (WDS), the ISC Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA), the Research Data Alliance (RDA), University of Botswana (UoB) and the Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf), IDW 2018 combined the 12th RDA Plenary Meeting, the bi-annual meeting of the research data community, and SciDataCon 2018, the scientific conference addressing the frontiers of data in research. In a hyper-connected world where the Internet is pervasive and web technologies are driving major changes in our lives, research has become more than ever before digital and international. With the theme of 'The Digital Frontiers of Global Science', this landmark event was a rich week of science and data, featuring world renowned keynote speakers, plenary panels and discussions, and the presentation of high quality research and practical working sessions for international collaborations.</p>				
Organisers	Botswana Open Science and Open Data Forum, Research Data Alliance				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus (remote participation)				
What	Presentation on homomorphic encryption technologies				
Dissemination	Twitter	Public	Data scientists, researchers, industry leaders, entrepreneurs, policymakers and data stewards		
Event material	Website				

2.1.8 Blockchain for Development : The Future Now

When	7 November 2018	Where	Cluj-Napoca, Romania	Venue	
Topics	Blockchain innovation				
Details	The Blockchain for Development: The Future is Now Forum featured speakers coming from diverse fields to discuss a wide range of topics including decentralized data, smart contracts, health records storage, digital identity, social credits, international remittances, self-sovereign identity and showcased blockchain-based projects tackling common international development issues such as international aid transparency and traceability, climate change induced poverty, data loss and data theft, political corruption and others				
Organisers	Development Aid				
Who	Mirko de Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Speaker				
Dissemination	Witter, Facebook, LinkedIn	Public	Technology implementers, innovators and influencers in blockchain and DLT, alongside delegates from international organizations and representatives of local government met at the Blockchain for Development		
Event material	Website				

2.1.9 European Big Data Value Forum

When	12-14 November 2018	Where	Vienna, Austria	Venue	Siemens Conference Center
Topics	Data driven AI for the future, "From data protection and privacy to fairness and trust: the way forward" – Best practises and lessons from the Big Data Value PPP				
Details	The European Big Data Value Forum included keynotes and presentations ranging from cutting-edge industrial applications of Big Data technologies, artificial intelligence, innovative business cases of the data economy, inspiring future visions, and insights on EU policy-making and R&D&I funding in this area. Ideas exchanged at the European Data Forum have an impact on the design of future research and innovation programmes and policy decisions both at the EU and Member States level. This will drive data-driven innovation further and strengthen the European data economy as well as enhancing its positioning worldwide.				
Organisers	Big Data Value Association, e-Sides				
Who	Edwin Morley-Fletcher, Lynkeus				
What	Speaker				
Dissemination	Twitter	Public	researchers, technologists, policy makers, SME and industry representatives		
Event material	Website				

2.1.10 Blockchain in Sanità

When	12 November 2018	Where	Rome, Italy	Venue	<i>Istituto Superiore di Sanità</i>
Topics	Blockchain and public health				
Details	The event offered a scenario for debating current experiences, potential use cases and remaining challenges for the adoption of the blockchain technology in the healthcare domain, fuelling the debate among researchers, clinicians, technologists, policy makers, industry and citizens.				
Organisers	McCANN HEALTH ITALIA, Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Cittadinanzattiva, Wired Italy.				
Who	Mirko De Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Speaker, presentation “L'esperienza italiana del progetto My Health My Data” (transl. “The Italian experience of the My Health My Data project”)				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook	Public	researchers, clinicians, technologists, policy makers, SME and industry representatives, citizens		
Event material	Website				

2.1.11 MHMD Blockchain in Healthcare

When	19 November 2018	Where	London, United Kingdom	Venue	Queen Mary University of London
Topics	MHMD value proposition for hospitals				
Details	The meeting was designed to outline the features and potential of the MHMD platform for clinical research and medical care. The meeting illustrated the hospital engagement process, the opportunities for data mobilisation, measures for GDPR compliance, data privacy and security, advantages and caveats of the blockchain technology in healthcare, generation of synthetic data and potential applications in the clinics.				
Organisers	The MHMD consortium				
Who	All consortium representatives				
What	Open sessions and workshops dedicated to specific themes				
Dissemination	Website , Twitter, Facebook, Eventbrite	Public	Clinicians upon invitation		
Event material	Website page, print-based program, presentations				

MHMD Blockchain in Healthcare represented the first public meeting specifically dedicated to illustrating the MHMD value proposition for clinical centres. The event was articulated through key sessions devoted to major project themes (*Blockchain in healthcare, GDPR for Data Controllers, secure computing methodologies, privacy-preserving techniques, synthetic data*) and provided solutions, along with workshops dedicated to a more in-depth discussion on the implemented technical solutions by IT researchers, developers, clinicians and legal experts of the MHMD Consortium. The meeting was held at the presence of all MHMD partners and some additional stakeholders (external clinicians from Policlinico Gemelli Italian Research Hospitals, Queen Mary University London and Great Ormond Street Hospital).

The meeting aimed at presenting a variety of possible value propositions for hospital data providers, including *trusted data sharing, GDPR compliance, consent management, security and privacy preserving tools, analytics*, as well as opportunities for *data commercialisation*, with the

ultimate objective of tearing down barriers and gathering feedback for overcoming remaining concerns about risks, costs and liabilities of clinical data sharing. Plenary sessions and workshops focused on MHMD-developed tools including *blockchain*, *privacy preserving tools*, *synthetic data*, and *metadata catalogue*, so to make the underlying value clearer and more tangible to an external attendee.

The meeting was introduced by Steffen Petersen (QMUL), while the value propositions were summarised by the Project Coordinator, Edwin Morley-Fletcher. The relevant agenda is reported below.

Attendees showed a great deal of interest for the project and provided fruitful feedback. According to them, the most appealing value proposition was represented by the creation of a *data sharing trusted environment* enabling smoother interaction with commercial partners for access and usage of data. Also, *consent management tools* via mobile applications, able to simplify interactions with patients when additional consent is needed, were well appreciated.

More generally, the meeting was a success, and attendees expressed their interest in following up the discussion with the involvement of NHS trusts representatives.

2.2 Dissemination events in Y3 (M25-M30)

2.2.1 Atelier Avenir Sante Numérique

INVITATION

Etienne Caniard,
président du Fonds Avenir Sante Numérique,
à le plaisir de vous inviter à l'atelier

Blockchain et
mutualisation
des données,

Atelier
**AVENIR SANTÉ
NUMÉRIQUE**

Mardi 15 janvier 2019
de 12h30 à 14h30

When	15 January 2019	Where	Paris, France	Venue	Fondation de l'Avenir
Topics	Blockchain and data sharing				
Details	The objective of the group "Avenir Santé Numérique" at Fondation de l'Avenir is to federate the various players in the social economy, the industrialists concerned by the digital revolution in the field of health and the actors of medical research. In this context, David Manset (Gnùbila) was invited to showcase MHMD within a digital health-dedicated event.				
Organisers	Fondation de l'Avenir				
Who	David Manset, gnùbila				
What	Speaker, presentation of MHMD with demonstration of the blockchain platform for personal data, GDPR-compliant exchanges				
Dissemination	Twitter	Public	Healthcare professionals, researchers, industry and SME		
Event material	Website , press releases				

2.2.2 Blockchain Summit Frankfurt 2019

When	26 March 2019	Where	Frankfurt, Germany	Venue	Kap Europa Convention Center
Topics	Innovative blockchain developments within enterprise				
Details	The Blockchain Summit Frankfurt provided a platform to discuss the opportunities of blockchain technology with thought-leaders and industry experts, on sectors including Finance, Insurance, Retail, Supply Chain and Telecoms through intimate roundtables, interactive case studies and panel discussions. Blockchain Summit is the largest dedicated Blockchain for Business event in Europe, focusing on the industries most impacted by blockchain technology.				
Organisers	Nexus				
Who	Mirko de Maldè, Lynkeus				
What	Presentation "Blockchain applications in healthcare"				
Dissemination	-	Public	Global influencers in technology, civil society, democracy promotion and innovation		
Event material	Website				

2.2.3 e-HealthWorld Monaco 2019

When	26-27 March 2019	Where	Principality of Monaco	Venue	Hotel Fairmont
Topics	State of the art and future of eHealth				
Details	Placed under the high patronage of Prince Albert II of Monaco, e-HealthWorld aims to establish an inventory of technological advances in the field of health and well-being, medical disciplines, but also to assess potential advances. It will bring together new patients (empowerment), MedTech and Pharma (drug Tech) manufacturers, but also payers (insurers and mutuals) and regulators. The appointment is now recognized by both healthcare professionals and industry for its high scientific level.				
Organisers	Principality of Monaco				
Who	David Manset, gnùbila				
What	Speaker in the session "e-SANTE ET BLOCKCHAINS" (26 March 2019, 16h30 - 18h00), with the presentation "BLOCKCHAINS ET RGPD"				
Dissemination	Twitter	Public	Healthcare professionals, pharmacists, researchers, students, patients, industry and SME, payers, regulators		
Event material	Website , press releases				

2.2.4 RDA 13th Plenary Meeting

When	2-4 April 2019	Where	Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA	Venue	Loews Hotel Philadelphia, Drexel University
Topics	<i>"With Data Comes Responsibility"</i>				
Details	With the theme, "With Data Comes Responsibility," P13 explored how the international, inter- and transdisciplinary nature of RDA has helped to lay a foundation for global partnerships and addressing responsibility throughout the data-lifecycle and across all domains. Known for its track record of success represented by strong attendance, concrete outcomes, and overwhelmingly positive meeting satisfaction and value for attendees, RDA Plenaries are consistently successful in facilitating the international RDA data community in connecting data conversations across the globe and among all disciplines.				
Organisers	Research Data Alliance-United States in partnership with Drexel University				
Who	Mirko de Maldè, Davide Zaccagnini, Ludovica Durst, Lynkeus				
What	Mirko De Maldè - Chair of "Blockchain in healthcare" Working Group with presentation of MHMD				
Dissemination	-	Public	Data professionals, researchers, industry leaders, entrepreneurs and policymakers		
Event material	Website				

2.2.5 ITASEC 19

ITASEC19

ITALIAN CONFERENCE ON CYBERSECURITY

Pisa, 12-15 February 2019

When	12-15 April 2019	Where	Pisa, Italy	Venue	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
Topics	Cybersecurity				
Details	The 2019 edition of ITASEC gathered Italian researchers and professionals working in the field of cybersecurity, from both private and public sectors and include academia, industries, research institutions, and government.				
Organisers	CINI – Cybersecurity National Lab				
Who	Enrico Cambiaso (plus, Ivan Vaccari and Maurizio Aiello as authors of the presented research work)				
What	Presentation of the research paper Cambiaso, E., Vaccari, I., Patti, L. & Aiello, M. Darknet Security: A Categorization of Attacks to the Tor Network				
Dissemination	-	Public	Academics, industry representatives, policy makers		
Event material	Event page , workshop proceedings				

2.3 Upcoming (M31-M36)

2.3.1 Healthcare IT Workshop Montpellier

UNIVERSITÉ DE MONTPELLIER

When	24 May 2019	Where	Montpellier, France	Venue	<i>Université de Montpellier</i>
Topics	Healthcare IT, with specific focus on blockchain in healthcare				
Details	The workshop, organised by the University of Montpellier, is focused on research related to IT in healthcare, at the presence of healthcare professionals and academics in the field. Within the event, a special roundtable is envisaged on use cases of blockchain in the healthcare domain.				
Organisers	Roxana Ologeanu-Taddei, Associate Professor, Université de Montpellier				
Who	Anna Rizzo, Lynkeus				
What	Presentation of MHMD within the roundtable “Beyond the technique, the cases uses of blockchain and innovation in healthcare”				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn	Public	Healthcare professionals, researchers in social sciences, researchers in Information Systems security and privacy		
Event material	-				

2.3.2 MyData 2019

When	25-27 September 2019	Where	Montpellier, France	Venue	Université de Montpellier
Topics	"Rebuilding trust - for human-centered data economy"				
Details	MyData Global's mission is to empower individuals by improving their right to self-determination regarding their personal data. The human-centric paradigm is aimed at a fair, sustainable, and prosperous digital society, where the sharing of personal data is based on trust as well as balanced and fair relationship between individuals and organisations. MyData 2019 conference is a place for accelerating global change towards a human-centric approach to personal data. On 25-27 September 2019, some 1000 experts from business, legal, tech and society sectors will gather for the fourth time in Helsinki, with the focus on how to effect the change we need.				
Organisers	MyData Global				
Who	TBD – Presence not confirmed Possibly Anna Rizzo, Lynkeus and a representative from UTBV or Athena RC				
What	This year, a panel proposal for the event was submitted by Dr Nicolo Zingales (Lecturer in Competition and Information Law, Sussex European Institute, University of Sussex) with the support of Lynkeus (Anna Rizzo), with the title "Keeping control and minimizing risk in secondary usage of health data", focused on consent and privacy management of individuals' data, privacy preserving technologies and secure computation algorithms, as well as new forms of collective data control ("our data") initiatives by the patient community. If accepted, the panel will encompass the presence of one member of the PC's team (TBD) and/or one representative from UTBV or Athena RC (TBD) as speakers.				
Dissemination	Website, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn	Public	Industry and SME, start-ups, legal experts, technologists and civil society at large		
Event material	Website				